

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
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***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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POTENTIAL OF HYALURONIC ACID IN THE TREATMENT OF CHRONIC CYSTITIS OF VARIOUS ETIOLOGIES**Azimov S.I.**

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Resume. *This scientific study involved patients with chronic recurrent cystitis who had not achieved successful outcomes from previous treatments. The study evaluated results in patients who received antibiotics based on sensitivity determined by bacteriological urine analysis, as well as in those who simultaneously received hyaluronic acid.*

Keywords: *recurrent chronic cystitis, bladder tuberculosis, intravesical instillation of hyaluronic acid.*

ТУРЛИ ЭТИОЛОГИЯЛИ СУРУНКАЛИ ЦИСТИТНИ ДАВОЛАШДА ГИАЛУРОН КИСЛОТАСИНИНГ ИМКОНИЯТЛАРИ**Азимов С.И.**

Абу Али ибн Сино номидаги Бухоро давлат тиббиёт институти, Бухоро ш., Ўзбекистон

Резюме. *Ушбу илмий тадқиқотда сурункали қайталанувчи цистит билан касалланган, аммо беморларга даво муолажаси кейин самара олинмаган беморларда утказилган. Беморларда сийдикнинг бактериологик текшириши натижасига асосланган ҳолда антибиотиклар сезгирлиги аниқланган антибиотиклар қабул қилинган беморларда ва шу билан биргаликда гиалурон кислотаси қабул қилган беморларда олинган тадқиқот натижалари баҳоланган.*

Калим сўзлар: *қайталанувчи сурункали цистит, сийдик пуфағи сили, сийдик пуфағига гиалурон кислотаси қўйиши.*

ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ГИАЛУРОНОВОЙ КИСЛОТЫ В ЛЕЧЕНИИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО ЦИСТИТА РАЗЛИЧНОЙ ЭТИОЛОГИИ**Азимов С.И.**

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Резюме. *В данном научном исследовании участвовали пациенты с хроническим рецидивирующим циститом, у которых не было получено положительного эффекта от предыдущего лечения. Результаты исследования оценивались у пациентов, получавших антибиотики, к которым была установлена чувствительность на основании бактериологического анализа мочи, а также у пациентов, одновременно получавших гиалуроновую кислоту.*

Ключевые слова: *рецидивирующий хронический цистит, туберкулёз мочевого пузыря, инстилляция гиалуроновой кислоты в мочевой пузырь.*

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There are numerous publications dedicated to urinary disorders in women suffering from recurrent urogenital tract infections; however, a solution to this serious problem has not yet been found [1]. In most cases, the main uropathogens of infectious-inflammatory pathology of the urinary tract are *E. coli* and other gram-negative enterobacteria [2-4]. The leading clinical manifestations of this pathology are chronic pain, dysuria, and psycho-emotional disorders. Chronic pain negatively affects women's health and quality of life. Prolonged and unsystematic therapy exacerbates the situation, negatively impacting the psychological state and leading to the development of adverse side effects from medication use. The aforementioned aspects contribute to the difficulties in treating this group of patients.

Damage and dysfunction of the urothelium can lead to a number of bladder disorders and diseases, including frequent urination, urinary urgency, urinary incontinence, and chronic pain. One of the protective mechanisms ensuring the proper functioning of the urothelial epithelium is the presence of a protective layer of glycosaminoglycans (GAG). The GAG layer is a thin, waterproof polysaccharide coating that plays an insulating role. It separates sensitive urothelial cells from urine irritants (urea, potassium ions, and drug metabolites) and potential infectious agents (especially bacteria). It consists of many polysaccharides, including hyaluronic acid, chondroitin sulfate, heparan sulfate, dermatan sulfate, keratan sulfate, and heparin. These polysaccharides combine with urothelial proteins to form proteoglycans. Damage to the protective GAG lay-

er covering the bladder mucosa is an important link in the pathogenesis of chronic inflammatory bladder diseases, as well as a triggering cause of the clinical manifestations of these conditions [5].

Furthermore, prolonged inflammation alters the sensitivity of molecular receptors in neighboring nerve tissues, making it difficult to treat chronic pain syndrome.

The European Association of Urology [4] in its guidelines recommends the use of hyaluronic acid and chondroitin sulfate instillations to replenish the glycosaminoglycan layer (GAG) in the treatment of interstitial cystitis, overactive bladder, radiation cystitis, as well as for the prevention of UTI recurrence.

The aim of the study was to assess the effectiveness of intravesical instillations of high molecular weight hyaluronic acid (HMWHA) in reducing the frequency of urinary tract infection (UTI) recurrences and the presence of side effects.

The study was conducted at the urology departments of the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Bukhara State Medical Institute, and the urogenital department of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Phthisiology and Pulmonology of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This was an open prospective study, examining 100 patients diagnosed with recurrent chronic cystitis and 15 patients with bladder tuberculosis. The average age of the patients was 43.6 ± 7.8 years (range 35-58 years). The frequency of disease exacerbations throughout the year was 11.3 ± 7.3 times. In all patients, the symptoms were persistent, with urination frequency of more than 8 times a day, frequent disease relapses, and low quality of life. All patients had extensive long-term treatment experience for their condition, without satisfactory effect.

Patients were divided into 2 groups, which were compared according to all main criteria: age, somatic, obstetric, and gynecological history, bad habits, etc. The first group consisted of 100 patients with nonspecific interstitial cystitis, the second group - 15 patients with bladder tuberculosis who underwent anti-tuberculosis chemotherapy according to directive documents. In both groups, bladder instillations were performed with a sterile 0.16% sodium hyaluronate solution of 80 mg (Instilana®) in a volume of 50 ml (high molecular weight of 2 kDa), and antibacterial therapy was administered according to the sensitivity established by bacterial urine culture.

The study used generally accepted clinical, laboratory, and instrumental research methods. The examination of patients included collecting complaints, medical history, radiological urological examination when indicated, and cystoscopy. To assess the severity of dysuria and pain syndrome, voiding diaries and a visual analog pain scale (VAS) were used.

Comparative analysis of quantitative variables characterizing the clinical, laboratory, and functional state of the urinary system was carried out using descriptive statistics with the Wilcoxon nonparametric test. When describing qualitative characteristics, the chi-square test was used. For characterizing the qualitative attribute of data distribution, the standard error of proportion (m) was used in calculations, and for quantitative attributes - the standard deviation (σ). Data processing and graphical representation were carried out using Statistica 6.0 and Excel 2007 software.

Patients received bladder instillations once a week with a 0.16% sodium hyaluronate solution in an amount of 50 ml for 4 weeks. Patients were required to retain urine for at least 2 hours after instillation. Patients were informed about the purposes and specifics of the procedure and signed informed consent. Patients filled out the voiding diary 3 days before the first and last instillation. Bacterial urine culture was performed at the beginning and end of therapy. Adverse events were assessed during each visit. For a year after the completion of treatment, the patients were under follow-up observation.

Research results. Analysis of the nature of patients' complaints, taking into account nosological groups over time, before and after treatment, revealed the following. The frequency of pollakiuria in the observation groups decreased 19-fold, by 94.8%; specifically, in the first group, the indicator decreased 25-fold, and in the second group, 7.5-fold. The frequency of imperative urges to urinate in the groups after treatment decreased 9.7-fold, by 45.2%. For the first group, this indicator decreased 7-fold, for the second group, 8-fold. All patients from the nosological groups, before treatment, up to 88.7% of patients complained of pain above the pubic area. After treatment, this indicator decreased by 83.5%. In the first group, the occurrence of pain above the pubic area decreased by 28 times, in the second group by 7.5 times. Before the start of treatment, 87.2% of patients were bothered by pain during bladder filling, after treatment, this indicator decreased to 4.3%. The frequency of urethral discomfort and burning after treatment decreased by 10 times to 5.2% for both groups. The frequency of dyspareunia for both groups as a result of treatment decreased by 12.4 times, by 70.4%. The duration and intensity of the manifestation of the above-mentioned complaints caused emotional lability in patients with chronic cystitis in 57.4% of cases. Often, they initially did not believe in the success of the proposed treatment, having unfavorable long-term experience with previous therapy. Emotional lability was quite pronounced in all groups, with no statistically significant differences found.

However, after treatment, the frequency of this indicator for both groups decreased by 9.4 times to 6.1%. In the first group, this indicator decreased by 14.2 times, in the second group by 3.7 times (Table 1). Terminal hematuria was observed in 25% of cases in the 1st group and in 100% of cases in the second group. During treatment, patients in group 1 visually noted improvement in their condition and cessation of hematuria, but in 3 patients, after the 4th instillation, burning and slight macrohematuria reappeared, which stopped on its own. Patients from the 2nd group also noted improvement in their condition and cessation of hematuria, but in 2 patients, recurrence of hematuria was noted after the 3rd-4th procedure of urinary bladder instillation with 0.16% sodium hyaluronate solution in an amount of 50 ml. Overall, this adverse event was observed in 5 (4.3%) cases out of 115 patients.

Table 1

Complaints reported by patients with chronic cystitis from two nosological groups before and after treatment

Signs	All groups n=115		I group, n=100		II group n=15	
	Abs. number	%	Abs. number	%	Abs. number	%
Pollakiuria	115	100	100	100	15	100
Before treatment	6	5,2*	4	4,0*	2	13,3*
After treatment	58	50,4	47	47	11	73,3
Urge incontinence	6	5,2*	4	4,0*	2	13,3*
Before treatment	102	88,7	87	87	15	100
After treatment	6	5,2*	4	4,0*	2	13,3*
Pain above the pubic area	101	87,2	86	86	15	100
Before treatment	5	4,3*	3	3,0*	2	13,3*
After treatment	62	53,9	48	48	14	93,3
Pain during bladder filling	6	5,2*	3	3,0*	3	20*
Before treatment	88	76,5	75	75	13	86,7
After treatment	7	6,1*	5	5,0*	2	13,3*
Discomfort and burning in the urethra	66	57,4	57	57	11	73,3
Before treatment	7	6,1*	4	4,0*	3	20*
After treatment	40	34,8	25	25,0	15	100
Dyspareunia	5	4,3*	3	0*	2	6,7*

Note: n - number of patients; * - differences are statistically significant (p<0.05)

The average bladder capacity, when analyzing the urinary diary, increased by 43 ml after treatment, while in the first group this indicator increased by 39 ml, in the second group by 61.7 ml. The average number of micturitions in the observation group after treatment decreased by 9.7 micturitions per day; in the first group by 10.4, in the second group by 9.5 times, the number of micturitions per day decreased (Table 2).

Table 2

Dynamics of urination diary data in female patients before and after treatment

Indicator	All groups n=115	I group n=100	II group n=15
Average urination volume in ml	137,8±12,4	146,3±13,1	125±15,3
Before treatment	180,5±12,4*	185,2±10,9*	186,7±12,3*
After treatment	16,2±26,3	15,6±4,8	16,8 ± 4,3
Number of urinations per day	6,5±1,2*	5,2±1,7*	7,3±1,9*
Before treatment	4,8±1,8	5,5 ± 1,7	4,1 ± 1,5
After treatment	2,1±1,3*	2,1±1,3*	1,3±0,6*

Note: n - number of patients; * - differences are statistically significant (p<0.05)

When completing the visual analogue pain scale and analyzing the obtained data, it was revealed that pain bothered patients from both nosological groups to varying degrees. After treatment, there was a pronounced positive trend: in some patients, the pain completely subsided, while the remaining patients noted a significant reduction in pain syndrome (Table 3).

Table 3

Severity of pain syndrome in nosological groups before and after completion of treatment (scores in %)

Pain intensity	I group n=100		II group n=15	
	Before treatment (%)	After treatment (%)	Before treatment (%)	After treatment (%)
Mild	10	88*	0	86,7*
Moderate	30	12*	26,7	13,3*
Severe	40	0*	40	0*
Very severe	20	0*	33,3	0*

Note: n - number of patients; * - differences are statistically significant (p<0.05)

During treatment, a decrease in the level of leukocyturia was also observed in both nosological groups (Table 4).

Table 4.

Dynamics of leukocyturia in nosological groups before and after treatment

indicator	All groups n=115		I group, n=100		II group, n=15	
	Abs. number	%	Abs. number	%	Abs. number	%
Leukocytes >4000 per 1 mL of urine before treatment	93	80,9	78	78	15	100
After treatment	11	9,6*	6	6,0	5	33,

Note: n - number of patients; * - differences are statistically significant (p<0.05)

The results of the control cystoscopy revealed a significant improvement in the bladder mucosa in both groups of patients. In the 1st group, the ulcerative lesion had completely healed, while in the 2nd group, it decreased to 1 (6.7%) case (Table 5).

Table 5

Results of cystoscopy in patients before and after treatment

Sign	All groups n=40		I group n=25		II group n=15	
	Abs. number	%	Abs. number	%	Abs. number	%
Hyperemia and edema of the mucous membrane, before treatment	38	95,0	20	80,0	15	100
After treatment	4	10,0*	2	8,0*	2	13,3*
Bladder mucosal ulcer, before treatment	14	35,0	3	12	11	73,3
After treatment	2	4,3*	0	0	1	6,7*
Vascular injection, before treatment	23	53,3	8	32	15	100
After treatment	3	6,5*	0	0*	3	20*

Note: n - number of patients; * - differences are statistically significant (p<0.05)

Overall, 108 (93.9%) patients reported a significant improvement in their well-being, a reduction in complaints, a decrease in the frequency of urges to urinate, and an increase in the intervals between cystitis exacerbations. In 7 patients (6.1%), no improvement in clinical condition was observed.

Table 6

Frequency of cystitis recurrence in groups, before and within a year after the end of treatment

Results (M±m)	All female patients n=115	I group n=100	II group n=15
Average number of cystitis recurrences per year before treatment, cases	11,3±7,3	10,1±3,5	12,5±2,9
After completion of treatment, cases	4,5±1,6*	4,3±1,1*	4,8±1,8*

Note: n - number of patients; *- (p<0.01) Differences before and after treatment are statistically significant.

The drug demonstrated good safety and tolerability. Only 4.3% of cases exhibited burning sensation and minor hematuria, which resolved spontaneously. No allergic reactions were observed during the monitoring period. Overall, within a year after treatment completion, the rate of cystitis recurrence decreased significantly, by more than 2-fold across all patient groups, which undoubtedly had a positive impact on our patients' quality of life (Table 6).

Discussion. The results of our prospective study confirm that intravesical HMWHA instillations in patients with chronic recurrent cystitis and bladder tuberculosis have significant clinical effectiveness. We noted significant improvements in both observation groups for all clinical signs, including bladder pain, hematuria, frequent urination, and the impact of urgent urges on quality of life. Damage to the protective layer of glycosaminoglycans (GAG) covering the bladder mucosa is an important link in the pathogenesis of chronic inflammatory bladder diseases, as well as a triggering cause of the clinical manifestations of these conditions [5]. Intravesical HMWHA instillations are a new therapy aimed at replenishing the protective layer of glycosaminoglycans to reduce urine exposure to damaged urothelium [6]. Our pilot study confirms the encouraging results obtained in previous studies of replacement therapy using HA for various diseases, such as interstitial cystitis/painful bladder syndrome [7-9], cystitis caused by intravesical immunochemotherapy [10], hemorrhagic cystitis after hematopoietic stem cell transplantation [11], and recurrent bacterial cystitis [12].

The results of numerous studies confirm the safety and effectiveness of HMWHA. These results confirm the findings of our research. Intravesical instillations of HMWHA in patients with tuberculosis showed high effectiveness. However, the number of observations in this group was small. Thus, the duration of response observed in our cohort 4 weeks after the last instillation is maintained in the medium term. Nevertheless, to determine how long the effect of HMWHA lasts, long-term observation of our cohort is necessary.

In a recently published study, hyaluronic acid and chondroitin sulfate instillations administered during radiation therapy ensured the prevention of urinary tract symptoms and improved quality of life after 1 year of observation [13]. The safety and good tolerance of intravesical HMWHA instillations were noted. Only two adverse events were recorded (6%; 2/30). These complications were two cases of hematuria, which were monitored and resolved spontaneously. In our study, adverse effects in the form of burning sensation and hematuria were also noted in 5 (4.3%) observations out of 115 patients. Both groups of patients (with recurrent chronic cystitis and bladder tuberculosis) also tolerated intravesical HMWHA instillations well.

Overall, 108 (93.9%) patients noted a significant improvement in their well-being, a decrease in complaints, a reduction in urinary frequency, and an increase in the intervals between exacerbations of cystitis. In 7 patients (6.1%), no improvement in clinical condition was noted.

Conclusion. Preliminary data showed that intravesical HMWHA instillations are effective in the treatment of recurrent cystitis and bladder tuberculosis. The use of HMWHA allowed us to reduce the frequency of cystitis relapses in patients by 2-3 times. Also, a low frequency of adverse effects of up to 4.3% was noted. To confirm our preliminary results, further comparative studies with a longer observation period are necessary.

References:

1. Гаджиева З.К., Гомберг М.А., Григорян В.А., Газимиев М.А., Казиллов Ю.Б. Особенности диагностики и лечения беременных женщин с неосложненной инфекцией мочевыводящих путей и урогенитальными инфекциями //Акушерство и гинекология, 2018; 11: 146-151. [Gadzhieva, Z. K., Gomberg, M. A., Grigoryan, V. A., Gazimiev, M. A., and Kazilov, Yu. B. "Features

of Diagnosis and Treatment of Pregnant Women with Uncomplicated Urinary Tract Infections and Urogenital Infections." *Obstetrics and Gynecology*, vol. 11, 2018, pp. 146-151.]

2. Рашидов З.Р., Азимов С. И. Анализ распространенности неспецифической инфекции мочевого тракта у больных туберкулезом среди жителей Бухарской области Республики Узбекистан// *Урология*, 2024, №1, С.31-35 [Rashidov, Z. R., and Azimov, S. I. "Analysis of the Prevalence of Nonspecific Urinary Tract Infections in Tuberculosis Patients among Residents of the Bukhara Region of the Republic of Uzbekistan." *Urology*, no. 1, 2024, pp. 31-35.]

3. Рашидов З. Р., Азимов С. И. Распространенность и тактика лечения неспецифической инфекции мочевого тракта у больных туберкулезом// *Туберкулез и болезни лёгких*. – 2022. – Т. 100, № 5. – С. 43-47. <http://doi.org/10.21292/2075-1230-2022-100-5-43-47> [Rashidov, Z. R., and Azimov, S. I. "Prevalence and Treatment Strategy of Nonspecific Urinary Tract Infections in Tuberculosis Patients." *Tuberculosis and Lung Diseases*, vol. 100, no. 5, 2022, pp. 43-47. <https://doi.org/10.21292/2075-1230-2022-100-5-43-47>.]

4. EAU Guidelines. Edn. presented at the EAU Annual Congress Milan 2023. ISBN 978-94-92671-19-6).

5. Sławomir Poletajew, Magdalena M. Brzózka, Wojciech Krajewski, Hubert Kamecki, Łukasz Nyk, Piotr Kryst Glycosaminoglycan Re-

placement Therapy with Intravesical Instillations of Combined Hyaluronic Acid and Chondroitin Sulfate in Patients with Recurrent Cystitis, Post-radiation Cystitis and Bladder Pain Syndrome: A Narrative Review// *Pain Ther.* 2024 Feb; 13(1): 1–22

6. Wyndaele JJJ, Riedl C, Taneja R, Lovasz S, Ueda T, Cervigni M (2019) GAG replenishment therapy for bladder pain syndrome/interstitial cystitis. *Neurourol Urodyn* 38(2):535-544

7. Morales A, Emerson L, Nickel JC (1997) Intravesical hyaluronic acid in the treatment of refractory interstitial cystitis. *Urology* 49:111-113;

8. Shao Y, Shen ZJ, Rui WB, Zhou WL (2010) Intravesical instillation of hyaluronic acid prolonged the effect of bladder hydrodistention in patients with severe interstitial cystitis. *Urology* 75:547-550;

9. Ahmad I, Sarath Krishna N, Meddings RN (2008) Sequential hydrodistension and intravesical instillation of hyaluronic acid under general anaesthesia for treatment of refractory interstitial cystitis: a pilot study. *Int Urogynecol J Pelvic Floor Dysfunct* 19(4):543-546

10. Sommariva ML, Sandri SD, Ceriani V (2010) Efficacy of sodium hyaluronate in the management of chemical and radiation cystitis. *Minerva Urol Nefrol* 62(2): 145-150

11. Miodosky M, Abdul-Hai A, Tsigotis P et al (2006) Treatment of post-hematopoietic stem cell transplantation hemorrhagic cystitis with intravesicular sodium hyaluronate. *Bone Marrow Transplant* 38(7):507-511

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